

Formation of sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membrane on a biodegradable self-assembled monolayer of poly(lactic acid)

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Abstract

The utilization of biomimetic membranes supported by advanced self-assembled monolayers is gaining attraction as a promising sensing tool. Biomimetic membranes offer exceptional biocompatibility and adsorption capacity upon degradation, transcending their role as mere research instruments to open new avenues in biosensing. This study focused on anchoring a sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membrane onto a self-assembled monolayer composed of a biodegradable polymer, functionalized with poly(ethylene glycol)-cholesterol moieties, for lipid membrane integration. Real-time monitoring via quartz crystal microbalance, coupled with characterization using surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, provided comprehensive insights into each manufacturing phase. The resulting lipid layer, along with pores formed by the transmembrane protein gramicidin A, exhibited robust stability. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy analysis confirmed membrane integrity, successful pore formation, and consistent channel density. Notably, gramicidin A demonstrated sustained functionality as an ion channel upon reconstitution, with its functionality being effectively blocked and inhibited in the presence of calcium ions. These findings mark significant strides in developing intricate biodegradable nanomaterials with promising applications in biomedicine.

Keywords: poly(lactic acid), biomimetic membrane, self-assembled monolayers, surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy, gramicidin A

1. Introduction

The utilization of biomimetic membranes as models offers a simplified approach to investigating the structure-function relationships of various biologically significant membrane peptides and proteins, thereby diminishing the complexity of *in situ* studies [1-3]. The versatility of biomimetic membranes extends beyond mere research tools; they hold immense potential for diverse applications, including their utilization as biosensors [4-6]. Their high biocompatibility and absorbability upon degradation pave the way for promising avenues in biosensing [7, 8].

Sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membranes (stBLMs) have emerged as valuable biomimetic platforms for supporting transmembrane proteins in biosensing applications [9, 10]. When formed on self-assembled monolayer (SAM) electrodes, stBLMs represent a synergistic approach that leverages the unique properties of each component to create a versatile platform. An stBLM consists of a lipid bilayer supported on a substrate through sparse, long-chain tether molecules. These tethers typically comprise an amphiphilic molecule, consisting of a lipid coupled with a hydrophilic spacer and anchoring group, facilitating their attachment to a pre-modified metallic surface. This structural configuration allows for the formation of a water cushion trapped between the electrode and the membrane [11]. Integration with a SAM electrode confers several advantages to the stBLM. The SAM provides a stable and well-defined surface for anchoring the stBLM, ensuring robust adhesion and facilitating precise control over the membrane's orientation and composition.

Furthermore, the SAM can undergo functionalization to incorporate specific chemical functionalities or biomolecular recognition elements, enabling customized interactions with target analytes or biomolecules. This capability proves particularly advantageous in biosensing applications. Squillace et al. developed a multipurpose electrochemical biosensor by employing a stBLM stabilized with molecular coatings consisting of diluted anchor-harpoon surfactants. These surfactants anchor the membrane using an alkyl chain emerging from a PEGylated-hydrogel layer, which serves as a soft hydration cushion [12, 13]. Moreover, the combined stBLM-SAM system provides a flexible platform for investigating membrane-protein interactions. Through the immobilization of membrane proteins within the stBLM and coupling with SAM-functionalized electrodes, researchers can delve into protein-lipid interactions, membrane protein functionality, and signal transduction processes with remarkable spatial and temporal resolution [14, 15].

Due to the remarkable sensitivity and specificity exhibited by certain transmembrane proteins, there has been a growing interest in leveraging them within biosensor platforms, leading to the conceptualization of ion channels as chemical sensors [16]. However, challenges arise in maintaining the stability of the lipid bilayer membrane and preserving the protein's functionality in environments different from its native ambient.

The incorporation of large transmembrane proteins into a stBLM needs an adequate space between the bilayer and its substrate, particularly due to the voluminous intracellular domains characteristic of certain proteins. For instance, the PIEZO2 ion channel dedicates 25% of its amino acid sequence to the intracellular domain, while members of the TRP ion channel family are known for their extensive intracellular domains [17, 18]. Introducing a polymer spacer between the SAM and the stBLM can facilitate the accommodation of such proteins. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) stands out as a hydrophilic polymer with minimal interactions with lipids or membrane proteins, rendering it promising for biomedical device applications and as a support for bilayer membranes. Although PEG is widely recognized for its effectiveness as a hydrophilic spacer [19]. It is worth noting that its chains tend to coil upon attachment to gold surfaces, which may potentially diminish the water content available between the lipid membrane and the solid support. However, the incorporation of stBLM has been demonstrated to alleviate this concern by reducing the surface density of anchoring molecules [9, 20]. Su et al. build a BLM featuring a PEG-lipid within the inner leaflet, situated on a gold electrode surface modified with 1-thio- β -D-glucose (β -Tg). Within this architecture, the PEG group serves as a spacer between the β -Tg SAM and the inner leaflet of the membrane, thereby establishing a water-rich layer in between [21]. Wagner et al. demonstrated the utility of a PEG cushion in anchoring a stBLM onto a quartz substrate, allowing the reconstitution of proteins like Cytochrome b5 and annexin V [22].

Incorporating SAMs' biodegradability for biosensor devices can significantly broaden their applications in the biomedical field while enhancing sustainability and biocompatibility. Among the most widely used biodegradable materials in biomedical biosensing is poly(lactic acid) (PLA), valued for its biocompatibility and absorbability within the human body [23, 24]. Moreover, PLA's outer surface can undergo partial hydrolysis, yielding carboxyl or hydroxyl groups. These surface alterations not only enhance biocompatibility [25] but also facilitate functionalization. Thus, while

maintaining mass properties, these modifications grant PLA with essential qualities for serving as a foundational material for SAMs, particularly in biomedical contexts.

Scheme 1. Comprehensive overview of the manufacturing procedure for a sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membrane (stBLM) connected to a self-assembled monolayer (SAM) on a gold substrate, incorporating poly(lactic acid) (PLA), and subsequently, surface functionalized by the incorporation of NH_2 -PEG-Chol structural units.

The present study outlines the effort to fabricate a stBLM on a modified PLA surface, aiming for its prospective application in biodegradable biosensors. Initially, a SAM is constructed

on a gold electrode surface modified with thiolated poly(lactic acid) (PLA-SH) and β -Tg (Scheme 1a-b), enhancing biodegradability of the system. The lipid membrane attachment is achieved through partial functionalization of PLA with PEG molecules terminated with cholesterol (Scheme 1c-e), facilitating their insertion into a DMPC/Cholesterol bilayer where the lipid termination serves as an anchor molecule for the stBLM (Scheme 1f). Additionally, we detail the reconstitution experiments involving gramicidin A (gA) protein to investigate ion channel formation within the lipid membrane. Explorations encompass conditions conducive to supported bilayer formation as well as pore generation. This system holds significant promise for advancing the field of electrochemical biosensors predicated on biomolecular principles.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

1-thio- β -D-glucose (β -Tg), hydrofluoric acid (HF), sodium tetrachloroaurate (NaAuCl_4), sodium thiosulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$), deuterium oxide (D_2O), sodium deuteroxide (NaOD) were purchased from Merck Life Science Sp. z o.o., Poznan, Poland. 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC) was purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids Inc., Alabaster, AL, USA.). 1,1,1,3,3,3-Hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) was purchased from Apollo Scientific Limit (UK). Cholesterol-PEG-NH₂ (>95 % and 3.4 kDa of molecular weight, NH₂-PEG-Chol) was purchased from Abbexa (UK). All other reagents and solvents, including *N*-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-*N'*-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), thiolated poly(lactic acid) (PLA-SH) and gramicidin A (gA), were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany.

2.2. Fabrication of polymeric self-assembled monolayers (SAM) on gold substrate

First, the gold electrodes, with a surface area of 0.09 cm², were cleaned and annealed in a flame after being dipped in a fresh piranha solution (H_2SO_4 : H_2O_2 3:1 v/v). In chloroform, solutions of PLA-SH (1 mg/2 mL) and β -Tg (1 mg/5 mL) were prepared, and then these two solutions were combined in a 9:1 v/v ratio. Before any use, the electrodes were incubated for 30 min in the mixture and then cleaned with Milli-Q water. β -Tg was utilized to increase the hydrophilicity and conductivity of the self-assembled monolayers (SAMs). This protocol is illustrated in Scheme 1 as steps a) and b).

2.3. Surface functionalization

The process of functionalizing the PLA SAMs with NH₂-PEG-Chol molecules was carried out using a concise three-step procedure previously reported by ours, with some modifications [26]. The initial stage involves the activation of the membrane surface by the utilization of alkaline hydrolysis (0.1M NaOH) for 30 min. During the second step, the gold electrodes containing PLA SAMs were immersed in a solution composed of EDC and NHS (1:1) at concentrations of 0.1 M and 0.2 M, respectively, in a phosphate-buffered saline solution (PBS) with a pH of 7.4. This procedure is necessary to generate amine reactive coupling groups on the surfaces of the PLA SAM. The carboxyl groups that were produced on the polymer surface, during the activation process using NaOH, underwent a reaction with EDC/NHS resulting in the creation of NHS ester groups. Thus, for the third step, the samples were initially subjected to a cleaning process using Milli-Q water to eliminate any residual NHS and EDC molecules. Then, the transamidation reaction involving the NHS moiety was conducted to establish a connection between the NH₂-PEG-Chol building block and the PLA SAM. The solution containing NH₂-PEG-Chol at a concentration of 1 mg/mL in PBS was introduced to the PLA samples and left to undergo a reaction for 4 hours. Therefore, amide linkages were obtained. Subsequently, the samples were rinsed to remove any molecules that did not participate in the reaction. For the sake of simplicity, the resulting product is referred to as PLA-PEG-Chol. Above-described modification procedure is illustrated in Scheme 1 as steps c), d) and e).

2.4. Preparation of gramicidin-embedded proteoliposomes and construction of sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membranes (stBLM)

DMPC phospholipid and cholesterol were dissolved in chloroform (7:3) in a glass vial to a final concentration of 10 mg/mL. Then, organic solvents were evaporated in a stream of inert gas (argon) and were further dried under high vacuum conditions for at least 48 h to form a thin lipid film. Later, 0.1 mg of gA protein was added to the lipid suspension and, subsequently, the lipid film was resuspended in 1 mL of PBS saline solution (pH-7.4) and incubated for 30 min at room temperature with gentle stirring. As-prepared proteoliposome, embedded with gA, was stored at 4 °C until use. The construction of a sparsely tethered lipid bilayer system involved the utilisation of a vesicle fusion technique. This technique entailed spreading gramicidin-embedded proteoliposomes onto a layer of tethered compounds. The PLA-PEG-Chol samples were

subsequently subjected to overnight incubation with the proteoliposomes, leading to the creation of sparsely tethered lipid bilayer systems on the surface of the functionalized PLA-PEG-Chol samples (see Scheme 1f).

2.5. Surface Enhanced Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy (SEIRAS).

SEIRAS enables molecular-level characterization of the films at the metal-electrolyte interface. In this method the electromagnetic field generated by the incident beam excites the local plasmon, creating an oscillating dipole in the gold nanoparticles situated on the flat surface of the silicon prism. This dipole generates an electric field in the proximity of the nanoparticle, capable of exciting the molecules adsorbed on the gold surface. The local electric field near the gold particles rapidly diminishes within a distance of several nanometers from the surface, a range comparable to the thickness of the membrane deposited on the electrode surface. Consequently, the absorption by the bulk solution is minimal. Additionally, this effect can be effectively nullified by collecting potential difference spectra. For SEIRAS measurements we have used Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) with MCT-A detector and custom-made single-reflection accessory. The spectral resolution was 4 cm^{-1} . Deposition of gold was carried out by dropping an aqueous plating solution onto the hydrogen-terminated Si surface. The plating solution was obtained by mixing 100 μL of 0.03 M $\text{NaAuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2 ml of 0.15 M $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3 + 0.05\text{ M Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} + 0.05\text{ M NH}_4\text{Cl}$, and 1 mL of 2% HF. After approximately 90 s of plating, the prism was rinsed with ultrapure water to finish the deposition. The deposited film underwent further modification by applying a mixture solution of PLA-SH and β -Tg (9:1) onto the gold surface. After a 30-minute incubation, the prism was gently rinsed with D_2O , and spectra were collected. Subsequently, NaOD was added to the prism, followed by a 30-minute incubation, rinsing again with D_2O . EDC/NHS (1:1) and NH_2 -PEG-Chol were then added to the prism and incubated for another 30 min, with each solution prepared in D_2O , and the prism washed with D_2O after each step. Adsorption spectra were collected after each step. After finalizing all modification steps, liposomes containing gA were introduced to the prism and left to incubate overnight, with adsorption spectra collected after 24 hours. The spectra are presented in absorbance units defined as $A = \log(I_0/I)$, where I_0 represents the intensities of IR radiation observed in the reference spectra, and I corresponds to the intensity observed for the sample. The reference spectrum consistently originated from the spectrum recorded in the preceding stage of prism modification. For instance,

in the case of lipid membrane spectra, the reference spectrum was derived from the spectrum of a gold-coated prism modified with PLA coupled with a NH₂-PEG-Chol. Data processing was performed using Omnic 9 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

2.6. Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM)

QCM measurements were performed using a model 400B time-resolved electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance (CH Instruments). Commercially available 8 MHz gold-coated AT-cut quartz crystals, with an area of 0.196 cm², were used as the functioning resonators. The specimens utilized in this study were fabricated on a circular substrate made of gold by the self-assembly method. The gold electrode's mass increased by 6.90 ng for every 1 Hz variation in frequency. The QCM cell underwent a 10-minute sonication in acetone, followed by washing with Milli-Q water before the measurements. Initial polishing of the gold QCM surface involved a 2-minute soak in piranha solution. After subsequent sonication in acetone for 10 min, followed by rinsing in ethanol and Milli-Q water, the crystals were finally ready for use. Once the frequency shift was less than 1 Hz (usually 1 h), the crystals were stabilised in PBS buffer (3 mL, pH 7.4) and mounted in a QCM cell. The solution containing PLA-SH/ β -Tg was injected into the QCM cell for self-assembly and further functionalization as mentioned before.

2.7. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

Peak Force QNM mode was used for Atomic AFM nanomechanical measurements with Dimension Icon (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA). In this mode, the force-distance curve is recorded for each pixel of the scanned area, and the z-piezo frequency is modulated at 2 kHz. This allows quantitative mapping of surface film mechanical properties. For imaging, ScanAsyst Fluid instruments with the standard spring constant ($K = 0.7$ N/m) were utilised. However, the sensors were calibrated using the thermal tune method before the experiment. The scan window sizes used in this work were 10 x 10 μm^2 .

2.8. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS analysis was carried out using an AUTOLAB-302N potentiostat coupled to a frequency response analyser. All measurements were performed with an amplitude signal of 10 mV (sinusoidal voltage) and frequencies ranging from 0.1 Hz to 10⁵ Hz. The EIS measurements were used in conjunction with a standard three-electrode cell. Using samples deposited onto a gold

substrate, all investigations were conducted at room temperature following the outlined methodology in the preceding sections. The reference electrode (RE) employed was Ag|AgCl|sat.(KCl), the counter electrode (CE) utilized was Pt wire, and SAMs placed on gold substrates served as the working electrode (WE) in a hanging meniscus configuration. The electrolyte employed was a solution of PBS buffer (pH 7.4). After data collection, the obtained EIS results were analysed using Nova software, which facilitated fitting the results to an electrical equivalent circuit (EEC).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of PLA- PEG-Chol self-assembled monolayers (SAM)

The establishment of a robust scaffold supporting artificial lipid bilayers followed a streamlined four-step procedure, as illustrated in Scheme 1. Leveraging amphiphilic molecules, specifically anchor lipids (NH₂-PEG-Chol), this approach provides a rapid and efficient means to functionalize polymer surfaces to tether lipid bilayers. Noteworthy for its exceptional biodegradability, biocompatibility, and bioabsorbability, the first layer is based on the well-known biodegradable polymer PLA [27]. In the initial step, a thiolated PLA monolayer is affixed to the gold surface. Subsequently, alkaline hydrolysis, employing sodium hydroxide (NaOH), activates the ester bond of the aliphatic polyester in the second step. The third step involves treating the resultant free carboxylic and hydroxyl groups of PLA with amine-reactive coupling agents, such as EDC and NHS. Finally, the N-hydroxysuccinimide ester (NHS-ester) formed readily engages in a reaction with amine-conjugated biomolecules, such as NH₂-PEG-Chol [26, 28]. Altogether, this procedure offers an ease way to obtain functionalized PLA nanomaterials in only four steps of synthesis.

Fig. 1. Procedures for functionalizing PLA as evaluated by Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM). Two lines represent the dissipation (blue) and frequency (green) measurements, respectively, and they correlate to the third harmonic (overtone).

The quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D) technique was employed to characterize the bioresorbable polymer platform. The QCM is a highly sensitive instrument used for measuring changes in mass per unit area within the range of nanograms to micrograms. The process entails monitoring the alterations in the resonance frequency of the quartz crystal after its stimulation by a driving voltage. As a result, the technique was employed to assess the surface modifications during gold functionalization procedures (Fig. 1). The supplementary material (Fig. S1) illustrates a graphical representation of diverse harmonics (overtones) for both frequency and dissipation monitoring. The material used as substrate for the QCM study was gold-coated quartz crystals. Thiols were employed in this study because of their well-established ability to form covalent bonds with gold, therefore, acting as anchoring molecules. Consequently, both thiol-terminated PLA-SH and β -Tg were used to form the SAM of PLA attached to the gold surface.

Then, as previously mentioned, the surface was treated with a solution of 0.01M NaOH to induce partial hydrolysis of PLA and to introduce free carboxyl and hydroxyl surface groups. The frequency exhibited an initial reduction that was directly proportional to the quantity of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) introduced into the system, as depicted in Fig. 1. Nevertheless, there was a further increase in value after two minutes. The cleavage of PLA's ester bonds through hydrolysis is ascribed to the presence of NaOH and it results in a reduction of a mass deposited on a sensor as reflected by frequency increase. Further, the excess NaOH was eliminated from the system by flushing it with water. Upon stabilization of the system, the subsequent step involved the addition of EDC/NHS and the formation of active NHS esters on a modified surface. The unreacted molecules were subsequently removed after 20 minutes during the continuous reaction. The reduction in frequency value upon this step becomes evident. The observed effect can be ascribed to the introduction of extra mass onto the surface of the PLA material. The coupling of NH₂-PEG-Chol was carried out next, the observed substantial drop in frequency can be attributed to the significant mass of NH₂-PEG-Chol, which possesses a molecular weight of 3400 Da. Fig.1 illustrates the dissipation graph of the system (dashed curve). The data reported in this study depicts the ratio of energy dissipated during oscillatory motion in relation to the total energy of the system. Overall changes in energy dissipation after subsequent stages of surface modification indicate variation in the viscoelastic properties of the immobilized film, which becomes softer upon functionalization.

A similar sequence of surface modification was performed on a silicon prism pre-modified with gold to check the correctness of the protocol. Completion of each step was monitored by SEIRAS measurements, which bring molecular-level information about the surface film and allow investigating the electrode-electrolyte interface [29]. Fig. 2 shows the SEIRA spectra recorded during subsequent modification steps of a PLA/ β -Tg coated gold electrode. In the first step (Fig. 2a), the substrate was treated with NaOD to generate free -COOH groups. The spectrum is dominated by the negative band located at $\sim 1762\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be interpreted as the loss of ester bonds as a result of hydrolysis in an alkaline environment. A negative band is also visible at $\sim 1456\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may reflect the reorganization of methyl groups as well as their loss as a result of the hydrolysis of ester bonds. In the next step, the substrate was exposed to EDC/NHS (Fig. 2b). In this case, the spectrum shows several characteristic bands in the range of $1800\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band with the highest intensity located at $\sim 1704\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is associated with the presence of NHS [30].

The absorption bands located at 1733 cm^{-1} and 1776 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ modes of the carbonyl groups of the succinimide ring, respectively. The band at $\sim 1646\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a visible shoulder may be an evidence of urea formation, which can alternatively form during the activation process [28]. The spectral features therefore indicate that activation of hydrolyzed PLA with EDC/NHS occurs. In the last step, Chol-PEG-NH₂ was coupled to the surface film. The spectrum shows a negative band at $\sim 1705\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reflecting the loss of NHS, a positive band at 1669 cm^{-1} corresponding to the urethane group connecting the cholesterol group with the PEG chain, and bands at 1623 cm^{-1} and 1563 cm^{-1} corresponding to amide I and amide II vibrations, which appear as a result of coupling of Chol-PEG-NH₂ with modified PLA. The intense band located at $\sim 1463\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirms the presence of cholesterol groups. In other words, SEIRA spectra confirm the successful modification of the substrate.

Fig. 2. SEIRA spectra obtained from a pre-modified gold surface with PLA-SH and β -Tg following treatment with (a) NaOH, (b) EDC-NHS, and (c) NH_2 -PEG-Chol.

3.2. Sparsely Tethered Bilayer Lipid Membranes formation (stBLM)

After the formation of a SAM consisting of two components, PLA-PEG-Chol on a gold substrate, it was transferred to a suspension of small unilamellar vesicles composed of DMPC and cholesterol, in a molar ratio of 7:3. The samples underwent an overnight incubation period to facilitate the formation of a stBLM on the modified SAM. The resulting stBLM was subjected to an initial morphological and electrochemical characterization later.

Fig. 3. Illustrative AFM topography images ($10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$) portraying the gold-supported self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) of PLA (left), alongside their respective indentation profiles delineated along the white dashed line (right). These images were captured under the specified

conditions: (a) PLA standalone, (b) PLA post-modification with PEG-Chol, and (c) subsequent to stBLM formation utilizing lipid vesicles composed of a DMPC and Cholesterol.

The AFM imaging technique was employed to observe the morphology of the stBLM at the early stages of lipid film development. Fig. 3 depicts the topographic images after each step of the formation of gold-supported SAM of modified PLA: (i) deposition of PLA SAM (Fig. 3a); (ii) its subsequent functionalization with PEG-Chol (Fig. 3b); and (iii) the final step involving the deposition of the stBLM (Fig. 3c). The samples were created using circular gold substrates, similar to those used in QCM experiments. After functionalization, lipid vesicles were deposited on the samples surface. It is noteworthy that the PLA surface exhibited the lowest degree of surface roughness, characterized by a subtly pronounced sawtooth pattern (Fig. 3a), which becomes more accentuated upon functionalization with PEG-Chol, as evidenced by the height profiles adjacent to each AFM image in Fig. 3. The introduction of the stBLM layer caused the increasing of the surface roughness due to the underlying imperfections from PLA-Chol topography, albeit it mitigates the sawtooth profile, attributed to the formation of a smoother layer through self-assembly (Fig. 3c).

Table 1. Roughness parameters from the surface analysis of AFM topography images of gold-supported self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) at various fabrication stages.

	RMS Roughness R_q (nm)	Mean Roughness R_a (nm)
PLA	23.5 ± 3.2	11.8 ± 1.6
PLA-PEG-Chol	27.4 ± 4.1	19.3 ± 3.2
PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC	37.2 ± 0.9	21.8 ± 0.1

Table 1 lists the surface roughness analysis conducted on the SAM surface at different fabrication steps. The root mean square roughness (R_q) increased from 23.5 ± 3.2 nm to 27.4 ± 4.1 nm, while the mean roughness (R_a) increased from 11.8 ± 1.6 nm to 19.3 ± 3.2 nm. This increase can be attributed to the rigorous alkaline hydrolysis of the PLA surface using NaOH, as well as

the presence of aggregated globular PEG-Cholesterol on the surface (refer to Fig. 3b). The globular aggregates formation was previously reported in a PLA membrane functionalization by PEG-Chol [26]. Upon the introduction of lipid vesicles onto the functionalized polymer substrate, a discernible thin layer was detected on the surface (Fig. 3c). Indeed, the presence of lipid layers led to a significant increase in surface roughness ($R_q = 37.2 \pm 0.9$ nm) as shown in Table 1, which probably belongs from the “worm-like” structures observed after the insertion of lipid vesicles.

3.3. Incorporating gramicidin A (gA) into a sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membranes (stBLM)

The incorporation of gA into the stBLM was performed by employing gramicidin-embedded proteoliposomes, derived from a DMPC/Chol mixture, which were then spread onto the surface of the gold-supported SAM of PLA-PEG-Chol. Leveraging the inherent fluorescence properties of the ion channel attributed to the presence of tryptophan residues, confocal microscopy was utilized to confirm its incorporation, as shown in Fig. S2. The resulting reconstituted stBLM surface exhibited a homogeneous distribution of the transmembrane protein gA along the surface with some dispersed channels' aggregation. Fig. 4 illustrates the SEIRA spectra acquired upon the final modification stage, i.e. deposition of lipid membranes composed of DMPC/Chol (Fig. 4a) and DMPC/Chol/gA (Fig. 4b). The spectrum recorded for the DMPC/Chol membrane shows characteristic absorption bands related to the stretching vibrations of C-H bonds, asymmetric ~ 2918 cm^{-1} and symmetric ~ 2851 cm^{-1} , respectively. The location of these bands indicates that the lipids are in a gel state and show a relatively high degree of order [31]. This observation is consistent with previous observations reported in the literature for DMPC/Chol composite membranes. Additionally, the spectrum shows a band related to the stretching vibrations of the C=O ester bond. The location of its global maximum, at approximately ~ 1739 cm^{-1} , indicates rather weak hydration in the region of the polar heads, which may also be partly due to the small amount of water accumulated by the PLA and PEG linkers separating the membrane from the electrode. Additionally, a band at ~ 1463 cm^{-1} is also visible, corresponding to the deformation vibrations of C-H bonds originating from both DMPC and cholesterol molecules, as previously observed in Fig. 2c.

The spectrum acquired for the DMPC/Chol/gA membrane (Fig. 4b) exhibits notable differences compared to the membrane without gA. While bands characteristic of stretching vibrations of C-H bonds are still present, both asymmetric and symmetric peaks are subtly shifted

towards higher wavenumbers. This shift may indicate slightly less order of lipids, but they nevertheless remain in the gel phase. Interestingly, the global maximum of the band associated with the vibrations of the C=O ester bond is shifted towards lower frequencies, which shows that the polar heads of lipids are slightly better hydrated in the presence of gA. This, in turn, may be the result of an increase in the amount of water at the interface due to the presence of ion channels.

Fig. 4. SEIRA spectra of lipid membranes composed of (a) DMPC/Chol and (b) DMPC/Chol/gA deposited on gold surface pre-modified with PLA-PEG-Chol.

Finally, the presence of the peptide in the membrane is clearly indicated by the presence of amide I band located at $\sim 1629 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is characteristic of the $\beta^{6.3}$ helix [32]. At the same time, a weak amide II absorption band is visible at 1537 cm^{-1} . However, its low intensity may come from the isotopic exchange, as a result of which the N-D vibration component is largely contained in a broad and complex band with a global maximum of 1456 cm^{-1} . This band is undoubtedly the result of the superposition of several vibrations, including the already mentioned N-D vibration in the amide bond, as well as C-H deformation vibrations, or other vibrations, for example, coming from the side chains of amino acid residues constituting gA. Nevertheless, the presence of the amide I band conclusively confirms the presence of the peptide in the membrane.

The electrochemical response at subsequent stages of electrode modification was monitored based on impedance measurements. EIS results, recorded at E_{OCP} , are represented in Fig. 5 in the form of Nyquist and Bode plots. Alternatively, the electrochemical response recorded at potentials of 0.1 and -0.1 V vs Ag|AgCl|sat.KCl reference electrode is available in Fig. S3. In

this case, it is possible to analyze the behavior of the system more comprehensively and obtain more quantitative information regarding not only the capacitance of the modified electrode, but also the resistance of the surface film. This can be achieved by fitting the experimental data obtained with the electrical equivalent circuits (EECs) that describe such results. These circuits, used for particular stages of the electrode modification along with the fitting results, are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 5. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, recorded at various stages of the stBLM fabrication on top of gold-supported PLA self-assembled monolayer (SAM), and after the loading of gA molecules: (a) Nyquist plots with the high-frequency region highlighted in the plot beside (a), and (b) Bode plots. All experiments were conducted in PBS electrolyte at a potential of 0.0 V vs Ag|AgCl|sat.KCl reference electrode using the hanging meniscus method. Experimental data are represented by symbols, while lines depict the fitting of the electrical equivalent circuits (EEC) showed in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of resistance (R) in $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ and constant phase element (CPE) in $\text{F cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{n-1}$ along with the empirical constant (n) reflecting the deviation from the ideal capacitor, for samples at each step of modification analyzed by EIS in PBS solution, obtained after fitting the electrical

equivalent circuit (EEC) are shown. The values of error corresponding to the fitted components are displayed in brackets.

	PLA	PLA-PEG-Chol	PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC	PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC-gA	PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC-gA/Ca ²⁺
R_1 ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	11.97 (0.41)	10.89 (0.79)	13.86 (0.53)	11.07 (0.40)	9.63 (0.42)
R_2 ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	—	384300 (10.08)	3492000 (14.64)	14400 (4.52)	367200 (6.73)
CPE_1 ($F \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{n-1}$)	1.43E-05 (0.39)	1.67E-05 (0.92)	5.97E-06 (0.46)	2.31E-05 (1.01)	2.52E-05 (0.48)
n	0.88 (0.08)	0.95 (0.18)	0.96 (0.09)	0.92 (0.17)	0.91 (0.10)
CPE_2 ($F \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{n-1}$)	—	—	—	4.23E-05 (1.73)	—
n	—	—	—	0.71 (2.51)	—

As Table 2 illustrates, the resistance value R_1 does not change significantly, which is understandable as it represents the resistance of the supporting electrolyte solution. More important are the changes in capacitance (represented by the constant-phase element CPE). In this case, it can be seen that the capacitance decreases after the lipid membrane is deposited onto the PLA-PEG-Chol film. As expected, after the introduction of gA, an increase in capacitance is observed. This effect is explained by the increased amount of electrolyte diffusion at the interface and within the film itself, as a result of the presence of ion channels. This is also confirmed by changes in the resistance of the surface film (R_2). Deposition of a DMPC/Chol lipid membrane on a PLA-PEG-Chol-modified electrode results in an increase in film resistance, while the introduction of gA causes a decrease in resistance in two orders of magnitude. The latter effect is most likely due to the formation of channels that enable the transport of ions through the membrane, significantly lowering its resistance.

Additional information can also be extracted from Bode plots (Fig. 5b). They present the dependence of impedance and phase angle as a function of the logarithm of frequency. Channels in the membrane formed by gA might be considered as defect sites. Their presence causes disturbances in the electric field during electrode polarization, which is manifested by the appearance of a minimum at the phase angle in the electrochemical impedance spectrum [33]. The impedance spectra for the PLA, PLA-PEG-Chol and DMPC/Chol membrane, show that the phase angle approaches a value close to 90 degrees at frequencies below 1000 Hz. Such result indicates the mostly capacitive behavior of the system reflecting the presence of a rather well-sealed dielectric layer on the electrode. When considering DMPC/Chol membrane the number of defects can be considered as small or negligible. The value of the total impedance also confirms the good sealing properties of the membrane. A different electrochemical response was observed when gA was introduced into the membrane. The value of total impedance decreased compared with intact lipid bilayer and its dependence on frequency displays a deflection point at ~ 100 Hz which is accompanied by the minimum of phase angle located at ~ 1 Hz. Such a minimum is characteristic of a membrane with defects. The latter results from the presence of channel-forming gA. The appearance of pores explains the decrease in total impedance as the membrane becomes more permeable. The position of the phase angle minimum remains roughly constant during the polarization of the electrode which corresponds to the situation where the density of the channels remains constant. Hence, the EIS response confirmed the incorporation of the ion channels into the lipid membrane.

To determine whether the observed phase angle minimum is due to the presence of gA ion channels, additional channel-blocking experiments were performed. For this purpose, impedance measurements were conducted in the absence and presence of calcium ions (PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC-gA/ Ca^{2+}). The Ca^{2+} ions are known as gA channel blockers [34]. The obtained results are depicted in Fig. 6. The Nyquist plot shows a significant difference in the impedance of the electrode modified with the DMPC/Chol/gA membrane (PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC-gA, Fig. 6a). The addition of calcium ions caused an increase in impedance, indicating hindered ion transport through the membrane, as evidenced by the important rise in surface film resistance R_2 (Table 2). Additionally, the changes in the phase angle of the Bode plot (Fig. 6b) show the disappearance of the characteristic minimum attributed to membrane defects/channels, suggesting that calcium ion introduction prompted channel blockage.

Fig. 6. Electrochemical impedance spectra due to the presence of calcium ions as inhibitors of the gA channel. Nyquist (a) and Bode plots (b) of stBLM on SME of modified PLA were obtained in PBS electrolyte at the potential of 0.0 V vs Ag|AgCl|sat.KCl. Experimental data are represented by symbols, while lines depict the fitting of the electrical equivalent circuit (EEC) showed in Table 2.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a stBLM was constructed to harness its potential as a sensor element being supported onto a SAM of biodegradable polymer, and functionalized with PEG-Chol as anchor points within the lipid membrane. The formation of the SAM was meticulously monitored and validated in real-time analysis using the QCM-D technique in conjunction with SEIRAS, enabling comprehensive coverage of all manufacturing stages. The resulting reconstituted and anchored stBLM exhibited pronounced surface roughness attributed to the dispersion of the PEG binding polymer, arranged in a globular fashion atop the PLA monolayer. The stability of the stBLM, alongside the formation of pores by the transmembrane protein gA, was consistently demonstrated across all manufacturing steps via SEIRAS and EIS techniques. SEIRAS analysis of PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC system indicates weak hydration around polar heads, likely due to limited water accumulation by PLA and PEG spacers. EIS results confirm good membrane sealing. In PLA-PEG-Chol-DMPC-gA system, SEIRAS reveals slightly less lipid order but improved hydration with gA, possibly from increased water due to gA channels formation. Transmembrane peptide presence was confirmed by SEIRAS and EIS. The latter also suggests successful pore formation

and a constant channel density by observing a reduction in impedance as membrane permeability increases and a phase angle stability during electrode polarization. Notably, the EIS results provide compelling evidence of the effective integration of gA into the lipid membrane, while preserving its functionality as ion channel. These findings hold significant promise for advancing the development of novel nanomaterials with diverse applications, ranging from drug delivery and biosensors to tissue engineering.

It is also important to highlight the advantages of the system discussed here, particularly when potentially used as a receptor layer, in comparison to similar membranes that incorporate gramicidin, as documented in existing literature. For example, Laredo et al. explored gramicidin in a supported bilayer on a Au(111) surface, revealing that the electric field can induce significant structural changes [35]. This study showed that direct contact with the metal surface stresses gA molecules. The stress is relaxed when the bilayer experiences relatively large negative potentials, leading to detachment of the membrane from the electrode and the formation of a thin water cushion between the metal surface and the bilayer. This stress issue can be alleviated using floating bilayer lipid membranes (fBLMs), which provide a more fluid and dynamic environment. Su et al. addressed this by studying gramicidin channels in fBLMs on gold electrodes [36]. Their findings indicate that the ion transport mechanism of gA is independent of the accompanying anion and that gA channels exhibit increased insertion and conductivity with decreased transmembrane potential. The fBLMs offer less stress on gA molecules due to the water-rich spacer between the bilayer and the metal surface, resulting in enhanced functionality of the ion channels. The stBLMs described in our work are considered a compromise between these two approaches, which results from the potential application of such systems in biosensing. The stBLMs demonstrate robust stability and sustained ion channel functionality when anchored onto a self-assembled film composed of a biodegradable polymer, enhanced by PEG-Chol functionalization. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and SEIRAS techniques confirm successful pore formation and membrane integrity, suggesting promising applications in biosensing due to their high biocompatibility and biodegradability. Overall, while stBLMs offer stability and biocompatibility for biosensing applications, supported bilayers show limitations due to stress from direct metal contact. Floating bilayers provide a less constrained environment, enhancing gA functionality and allowing detailed studies of ion transport mechanisms, but their usefulness for biosensing applications is limited.

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Supporting Information.

It contains quartz crystal microbalance analysis results of different functionalization steps of PLA, fluorescence micrograph of gramicidin A transmembrane protein distribution, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy results under potentials of 0.1 V and -0.1 V. The supporting file is available free of charge from the journal webpage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A.H.M. Mohammed-Sadhakathullah: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology. **P. Pashazadeh-Panahi:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology. **S. Sek:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **E. Armelin:** Supervision, Validation, Conceptualization. **J. Torras:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

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